

A STUDY ON IMPACT DAMAGE ANALYSIS AND TEST OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE FOR AIRCRAFT REPAIRABLE DESIGN

H. Park¹, C. Kong^{1*}, S. Lim¹, K. Lee¹

¹ Department of Aerospace Engineering, Chosun University, Gwangju, Rep. of Korea

* Corresponding author(cdgong@chosun.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Low velocity impact damage, Composite laminate, Damage tolerance*

Abstract

This study is focusing on the low velocity impact damage evaluation and the external patch repair techniques of carbon/epoxy UD and fabric laminate adopted developing aircraft. The impact damages of composite laminates of the carbon/epoxy UD and fabric are simulated by the drop-weight type impact test equipment. The damaged specimens are repaired using the external patch repair method after removing the damaged area. The compressive strength test and analysis results of the repaired specimens are compared with the compressive strength test and analysis results of the undamaged specimens and the impact damaged specimens. Finally, through investigation of compressive strengths of the damaged specimens at different environmental conditions, the damage criteria for repairable design of both the impact damaged UD and fabric laminate structure are suggested.

1 Introduction

As constantly increasing air traffic need for the general aviation aircraft, many countries have been developing various types of the general aviation aircraft. In Korea, the KC-100, which is a small scale piston propeller general aviation aircraft, has been developed to establish domestic certificate infrastructure and system through the BASA (Bilateral Aviation Safety Agreement) program with FAA by Korea Aerospace Industries, Ltd. This KC-100 aircraft adopted the whole composite structure concept for the environmental friendly purpose due to low fuel consumption by structure weight reduction as well as for the competitive aircraft market. However the carbon/epoxy composite structure, which is mainly used for this aircraft, is very weak against impact damage. Especially, the low velocity impact damage rather than the high

velocity impact damage cannot be easily found to investigate, so called 'barely visible impact damage'. Thus this type of impact damage of the composite structure has become an important issue in composite structure design. Several engineers have been performing various studies about the impact damages of the composite structure [1, 2]. This study is to investigate the residual compressive strength of the carbon/epoxy UD (Unidirectional prepreg tape) and fabric laminate due to the impact damages.

2 Experimental Test

2.1 Materials

The candidate composite materials used for the KC-100 aircraft are considered among some AGATE (Advance General Aviation Transport Experimental) materials which were proposed for increasing design reliability as well as promoting the small aircraft industry of the USA. According to this consideration, some composite materials, which are produced by Toray Industries Inc., are finally selected. Therefore, the wing spar is designed with carbon/epoxy UD prepreg (P707AG-15), and the main wing rib is designed with carbon/epoxy fabric prepreg (F6273C-07M).

2.2 Specimen manufacturing

In this study, specimens for spar and rib are manufactured by the autoclave molding process followed by the material supplier's recommendation. The lay-up sequence of the spar is 32 plies with $[45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{4s}$, and the lay-up sequence of the rib is $[(45^\circ/-45^\circ)/(0^\circ/90^\circ)]_{5s}$. Figure 1 shows dimension and impact location of the specimen. This dimension is taken according to ASTM D7136 standard.

2.3 Investigation of impact damage criterion for repair

According to a composite aircraft design handbook[3], the damage criteria are classified into five categories depending on the severity of damages for the damage tolerance design. The first category is the barely visible impact damage(BVID), and the second category is the visible impact damage(VID). Repair should be carried out from the second category. Thus the definition of the criteria for the VID category is important in structure design. In order to define the VID energy, this study produces impact damages with different impact energies in low velocity impact range, examines the visual finding possibility, and analyzes the decreasing tendency of compressive strength.

Environmental conditions are firstly considered before producing impact damages simulated on the specimens. The room temperature dry condition and the elevated temperature wet condition should be taken into account because degradation of mechanical property of the composite material may take place frequently by environmental conditions.

Fig. 1. View of UD laminate specimen

Fig. 2. Compressive test after impact with anti-buckling fixture

The specimens are immersed in a water tank with water temperature of 80°C which is to simulate the elevated temperature wet condition [4]. When the specimens absorb moisture until saturation, their compressive strengths are measured at before and after impact damage. As the range of low velocity impact energy is less than 10J, the impact damages are gradually carried within 10J for the UD and fabric laminate according to ASTM D7136[5], and their compressive strengths are evaluated. Finally, the damage criterion for repairable design of composite laminate is defined.

In case of the UD laminate specimen, the compressive strength test results in the room temperature dry condition show that the compressive strength of the damaged specimen at impact energy of 5J is reduced to 4% than the compressive strength of the undamaged specimen. The damage at this impact is started to find visually. It is reduced to 19% at impact energy of 6J and to 32% at impact energy of 7J. However, the compressive strength test results of the UD specimen in the elevated temperature wet condition shows that the compressive strength of undamaged specimen is reduced to 5% than the strength of the undamaged specimen in the room temperature dry condition. Furthermore, the compressive strength is reduced to 11% at impact energy of 4J, 17% at impact energy of 5J, and 31% at impact energy 6J.

Barely Visible Impact Damage(BVID) are defined as those which are visible at a distance of less than 1.5m and Visible Impact Damage(VID) defined as those which are visible at a distance of 1.5m. After 5J impact energy is applied, it was found that slight damage has occurred inside the specimen and, after application of 6J impact energy, the internal damage was so serious that the area was checked to require repair. Accordingly, as a result of checking, visual inspection was found to be valid.

In case of the fabric laminate specimen, the impact damages are produced within impact energy of 10J at the same environmental conditions as the previous case. In the room temperature dry condition, its compressive strength is reduced to 10% at impact energy of 5J and 25 % at impact energy of 6J which is possible to find visually the damage. As the previous UD laminate case, the strength test of the fabric laminate specimen also is carried out in the elevated temperature wet condition. The test results

show that the compressive strength is reduced to 25% at impact energy of 5J and 36% at impact energy of 6J. In this study, the anti-buckling device for the compressive test after impact was used. The compressive test after impact is illustrated in Fig. 2. Through the investigation above, the damage criteria for repairable design of composite laminate are suggested. Because the safety factor of 1.5 is used in most aircraft design, the repair of the damage tolerance structure can be performed at 33% reduction of its original strength. If this criterion is applied, the UD spar and fabric rib structure must be repaired if the structure has the impact damage equivalent to having impact energy of 6J in the elevated temperature wet condition.

3 Repair process

The external patch repair method, which is first removing damaged area and then repairing the removed area with external patches using adhesive, is chosen as the repair for both the UD composite spar structure and the fabric composite rib structure[6, 7]. Figure 3 shows external patch repair process to composite laminate structure.

Fig. 3. External patch repair process of impact damaged composite laminate

The patch was designed for a single sided repair of a 15mm damaged area on 100mm×150mm of composite panel. In the repair patch design approach, the lay-up sequence of impact damaged area was determined considering compressive strength. The dimension of the patch is 23mm×23mm and the patches having 4 plies were designed. The patch a prefabricated piece was adopted.

In order to investigate the strength recovery effect, the compressive strength of the repaired specimen is compared with the original specimen strength before impact damage. The compressive strength test of the UD laminate specimen is performed to investigate the compressive strength recovery effect of the repaired specimen by the ASTM D7137[8] standard procedure. The specimen before damage is fractured at an average compressive load of 215.80kN, but the specimen after repair is fractured at an average compressive load of 197.22kN. The test result shows that the compressive strength of the UD laminate specimen after repair is recovered to 91.39% of the compressive strength before damage.

The investigation of structural strength recovery of the fabric laminate specimen is carried out by the same ASTM D7137[8] standard procedure. In case of fabric laminate, the specimen before damage is fractured at an average compressive load of 168.96kN, but the specimen after repair is fractured at an average compressive load of 153.54kN. The compressive strength of the fabric specimen after repair is recovered to 90.88% of the strength before damage.

3 Finite element analysis

The finite element analysis is performed to compare with the test results mentioned above. The analysis models simulate almost the same shape of the repaired specimen using external patch. As for the boundary condition, the lower part fixed boundary condition of the specimen was applied equally to the specimen test condition and the load was applied in the longitudinal direction of the specimen in the upper part. Finite element analysis is performed using the MSC Nastran solver and finally the results are obtained in the form of stresses, strains. Total number of elements for FEM mesh generation were 3677 including 2637 for the patched region mesh. The lay-up sequence of the UD laminate for finite element analysis is 32 plies with $[45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_{4s}$ and the lay-up sequence of the fabric laminate for

finite element analysis is 20 plies with $[(45^\circ/-45^\circ)/(0^\circ/90^\circ)]_{5s}$.

The FEM analysis results are compared with the test results measured by the strain gage. In this paper, the strain when the specimen was fractured by compressive load was measured by the strain gage and then we compared the result of the strain measured by the strain gage with the result of the analysis. Finally recalculated stress considering elastic modulus from stain was compared the result of test with the result of the finite element analysis. The location of strain gage is a distance of 25mm from the top and side of specimen. Two strain gage locations of the specimen are shown in figure 18.

Table 1 shows the comparison of stress between the analysis results and the test results of repaired specimens. Through this comparison, it was found that the finite element stress analysis results are well agreed with the test results in both specimen cases of UD laminate and fabric laminate. Figure 4 shows stress analysis result of repaired UD laminate.

Table. 1. Comparison between test and analysis results of repaired specimens

	UD laminate		fabric laminate	
Stress	Test	FEM analysis	Test	FEM analysis
		84.7	97.8	131.8

Fig. 4. Stress analysis result of repaired UD laminate

3 Conclusion

This work carried out the low velocity impact damage experimental tests to find the structural design and repair criteria of the four-seated small aircraft, which will be used for BASA agreement with USA. Through the application of impact energies and the investigation of compressive strengths of the damaged specimens at different environmental conditions, the damage criteria for repairable design of both UD and fabric laminate structures are suggested.

The repair method using external patch is proposed to recover the reduced strength of the impact damaged specimens. Through comparison between the compressive strength of the repaired specimen and the original specimen strength before impact damage, the strength recovery effect is investigated. The validity of the finite element analysis model suggested in this study was verified through the comparative analysis of the stress between the specimen test results and the finite element analysis results.

References

- [1] C. T. Sun et al., "Quasi-static modeling of delamination crack propagation in laminates subjected to low velocity impact", *Composites Science and Technology* 53, pp 111-118, 1995.
- [2] J. J. Schutte et al., "Investigation of a cracked thick aluminum panel repaired with a bonded composite patch", *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 63(1999)305-323.
- [3] MIL-HDBK-17-3F, "Composite Materials Handbook", 2002.
- [4] ASTM D5229, Standard test method for moisture absorption properties and equilibrium conditioning of polymer matrix composite materials, 2004.
- [5] ASTM D7136, "Standard Test method for Measuring the Damage Resistance of A Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite to A Drop-Weight Impact Event", 2005.
- [6] Keith B. Armstrong et al., "Care and Repair of Advanced Composite", SAE International, 2005.
- [7] Alan Baker et al., "Composite Materials for Aircraft Structures", AIAA, 2004.
- [8] ASTM D7137, "Standard Test Method for Compressive Residual Strength Properties of Damaged Polymer Matrix Composite Plates", 2005.